
Original Research Article

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HERBAL BASED PAIN BALM FORMULATION FOR PAIN RELIEF

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Abstract-

The present research study is about to formulate the topical herbal balm for analgesic and anti-inflammatory activity. This present research showed a good effect for the animal suffering from pain. In this pain balm we used Lavender juice, Rosemary, Clove Oil and Ginger liquid drops which is very potent and effective.

Introduction-In common region common cold it seen the symptoms of nose getting block with mucous. For the common cold is arising to exposure to the environmental factor such as cold, dryness, dampness. By this our body affected by joint pain, headache, toothache etc. Many Scientists discovered many drugs but the present invention shows a different category herbal based balm which is used for the reduction of pain in in-vitro model.

Collection- The all samples are collected by me and Lavender juice, Rosemary juice, Clove oil and Ginger juice collected by my cousin.

Methods of Preparation-First add $\frac{1}{4}$ cup of an oil in a bowel after add 2tablespoons of beeswax to it. When heat the bases in the oven for around a minute, then they are completely melted. After use 15drops of camphor oil then microwave the mixture for 10seconds. After add 7drops of Lavender, 2drops of rosemary, 7drops of clove and 5drops of Ginger. After mix them in thoroughly and transfer the mixture to a storage container. Then leave it at room temperature to cool down. After it will be produced.

PH-For test the PH value 1gm of balm dissolved in 100ml of water. The PH value must be 5 to 6.9. The 1gm of balm with 100ml of water placed for 2hr and then dip the glass electrode. The measurement of PH value was 6.2

UV-Spectroscopy-0.1gm was taken after diluted with 10ml phosphate buffer 6.8 and shake to dissolve the balm in buffer. After solution filtered through whatman filter paper. 5ml of the filtrate was taken out and diluted to 50ml with buffer. After in UV-Spectroscopy the standard curve plotted 224nm. This UV-Spectroscopy determination done by a Lab in Bihar.

Result-

Experimental Animals-

In this research I never used the experimental animals I gave it to aayurvedic quack in Bihar. He used this formulation and gave it to the patients and according his inspection I saw this balm has no side effect, no skin irritation and it is very potent and effective. By this

formulation the patient's rheumatoid arthritis pain in-vitro sustained release in 20min for 1/9.6 day. But by this formulation headache in-vitro sustained release in 5min.

Skin irritation-

After applied this balm to the patients quack saw it has no skin irritation effect.

ADR-No side effect shown in this balm

Conclusion-After this experiment I say that this balm is very potent and effective for headache and it is potent and effective for arthritis and joint pain. It uses as analgesics and antipyretics sources.

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